

The Impact of Polarization on Infrared Sea-Surface Temperature Sensing

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Abstract – One of the most strongly polarized natural infrared sources is the sea surface, yet polarization is rarely considered in infrared radiometric sea-surface temperature sensing. For an off-nadir incidence angle, sea-surface emission is vertically polarized, and reflected atmospheric radiance is horizontally polarized. The net degree of polarization is determined by the relative magnitudes of reflected and surface-emitted radiances, which actually tend to offset one another because of their orthogonal orientations. The significance of partially polarized radiances on radiometric sea-surface temperature measurements is determined primarily by the viewing angle and the inherent polarization sensitivity of the radiometer. This paper discusses several ways that polarization can affect infrared radiometric measurements of sea-surface temperature. A specific example is shown, wherein the polarization sensitivity of a Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer results in small errors that are significant for high-accuracy radiometry.

INTRODUCTION

Polarization can be a significant factor in infrared radiometric sensing of sea-surface temperature when the radiometer views the surface at a non-normal incidence angle [1–5]. It is common, for example, for infrared radiometers mounted on a ship to view the sea surface at angles of 50° or more [6,7]. In some cases, the radiometer is pointed near the Brewster angle in an attempt to eliminate or reduce the reflected atmospheric radiance from the measurement [6]. In these kinds of situations, polarization should be considered from at least two viewpoints. First, sea-surface radiance becomes partially polarized when viewed away from nadir, so inferring a surface temperature from the measured radiance requires a polarization-dependent emissivity. Second, some instruments have a polarization sensitivity that cause errors if they view a partially polarized scene when calibrated for unpolarized radiances. Complicating the issue is the fact that the state of polarization of the measured radiance depends strongly on the radiometer's view angle, the surface roughness, and the atmospheric conditions, among other things. Therefore, the state of polarization is not a simple parameter to be estimated (or ignored) without careful thought.

STATE OF POLARIZATION FOR AN OCEAN SCENE

The scene radiance measured by a radiometer can be considered a sum of surface emission, reflected sky radiance, and atmospheric path radiance:

$$L_{\text{scene}}(\lambda, \theta) = \epsilon L_{\text{surf}} + R L_{\text{atm}} + L_{\text{sp}}, \quad (1)$$

where L_{scene} is the scene radiance, ϵ is the sea-surface emissivity, L_{surf} is the radiance emitted by the surface, R is the surface reflectivity, L_{atm} is the atmospheric radiance (including direct solar radiance, thermal atmospheric emission, and scattered solar and atmospheric radiance), and L_{sp} is the atmospheric emitted radiance from the short path between the radiometer and the sea surface (obviously, for a satellite sensor this latter path length is not so short). Every component of eq. (1) depends on wavelength (λ), and incidence angle (θ); only the short-path atmospheric emission term does not depend on polarization (except for possibly cases with extreme path scattering).

People often remember that reflection polarizes light, but do not realize that emission also polarizes light, even infrared emission. The concept of emission polarization was reviewed by Sandus [8]. Simply put, the polarization-dependent emissivity can be calculated as one minus the reflectivity. This complementary relationship between emissivity and reflectivity has a large influence on the state of polarization in an infrared ocean scene. Whereas reflected radiance tends to be horizontally polarized, the emitted surface radiance is vertically polarized. A simple conceptual picture of this arises from considering that the water molecules 'just below' the surface emit unpolarized radiance in all directions, which becomes partially polarized as it transmits through the water-air interface at non-normal incidence angle. The interface selectively reflects the horizontally polarized emission component back into the water, and therefore transmits more of the vertical component into the air.

The degree of linear polarization is defined as

$$dp = \frac{L^h - L^v}{L^h + L^v}, \quad (2)$$

where L^h is the horizontal polarization component of the

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radiance, and L' is the vertical component. The degree of polarization is a number with magnitude between 0 and 1, indicating totally unpolarized and polarized light, respectively. The number is positive for horizontal polarization, and negative for vertical polarization.

An increasing incidence angle increases the amount of linear polarization emitted by the sea surface because the polarization components of the emissivity diverge, as shown in Figure 1. However, the overall falling emissivity magnitude at larger incidence angles means that the reflectivity increases. Near 80° , the degree of polarization curve actually turns around and becomes rapidly more positive because the horizontally polarized reflected sky radiance begins dominating the vertically polarized surface emission. This is shown in figure 2, for a typical filter radiometer bandwidth of 8–9.4 μm (using the complex sea-water refractive index model of Friedman [9]). Of course what this means for surface-temperature sensing is that the apparent radiometric temperature of the surface falls as the radiometer is pointed to larger incidence angles, until it rises again near the horizon.

Figure 3 shows the degree of polarization calculated as a function of wavelength from the formulation of eq. (1) with a 1976 US Standard Atmosphere model and a smooth sea surface, viewed at 75° incidence. The wavelength range of this figure includes the two important atmospheric transmission windows of approximately 3–5 μm and 8–14 μm . Between those windows the atmospheric transmittance is nearly zero, producing essentially zero polarization.

The short-wave 3–5 μm window region is strongly affected by scattered sunlight, which totally dominates for wavelengths shorter than 3 μm . When scattered sunlight dominates thermal emission, the degree of polarization is positive (horizontal).

Figure 1. Sea-water emissivity for 0° and 60° incidence angles (h=horizontal, v=vertical polarization).

Figure 2. Degree of polarization (%) for a typical infrared radiometer band, calculated with a 1976 US standard atmosphere for a smooth sea water surface.

Figure 3. Degree of polarization (%) for a smooth sea surface and 1976 US standard atmosphere viewed at 75° .

In the long-wave 8–14 μm band, where scattered light is basically negligible, the degree of polarization is nearly always negative (vertical). A strongly emitting atmosphere, like a water-vapor-laden tropical atmosphere, and a wind-roughened sea surface also both tend to reduce the degree of polarization. Sun glints covering only 1% of the area viewed by the radiometer create strong positive (horizontal) polarization. The variation of the degree of polarization with these variables will be explored in depth in a pending journal paper.

EFFECT OF POLARIZATION ON RADIOMETRY

What effect a partially polarized scene has on a radiometric measurement depends on whether the polarization alters the

overall radiance level, as it does in the case of sea-surface temperature sensing, and whether or not the radiometer response varies with polarization state. As noted previously in the discussion of Figure 1, the apparent brightness temperature of the sea surface will decrease with increasing incidence angle, until extremely large angles are reached. An additional disadvantage of viewing the sea surface at large incidence angles is that the signal contains more reflected sky radiance.

The reflected atmospheric component can be reduced by viewing the surface through a vertical polarizer with a radiometer pointed at the Brewster angle [e.g., 6]. However, in practice this isolation does not work as well as originally hoped because it is essentially impossible to keep the radiometer pointed at the Brewster angle for all wavelengths in the instrument bandwidth from a moving ship on a rough sea surface. Also, the overall strength of surface emission at that angle is less than at normal incidence, and the polarizer reduces the incident radiance even further by at least a factor of 2. In addition, especially with imaging or wide-angle radiometers, calibration with a polarizer on the front end can be difficult [10]. These calibration problems can be lessened by designing the optical system specifically for polarimetric measurements [e.g., 11].

In some cases, such as with FTIR spectro-radiometers, the instrument polarization sensitivity is significant enough that achieving state-of-the-art radiometric accuracy with a partially polarized source like the sea surface requires additional polarimetric calibration. Measurements with our Bomem FTIR spectrometer, which uses the same interferometer as the popular M-AERI system [7], have shown a variation of instrument response between horizontal and vertical polarization states that ranges from about zero at wavelengths near 20 μm , to more than 10% at 5 μm . In the 8–14 μm region, the polarization sensitivity is 4–7%. The resulting error for viewing the sea surface at $\sim 65^\circ$ is on the order of 0.1 K. In the quest for increasingly high radiometric accuracy, this error is significant. Radiometric measurements that claim accuracy near 0.1 K with large incidence angles must consider the effect of polarization, and could possibly benefit from a polarimetric calibration.

CONCLUSION

Thermal radiance from the sea surface is partially polarized. The combination of emitted and reflected radiance components makes estimating the degree of polarization tricky, but also shows the importance of carefully considering polarization in many infrared radiometric measurements. Future research and publications will be forthcoming to clarify these issues. But for now, it is clear that the growing popularity of FTIR spectrometers, which are polarization sensitive, creates an especially strong motivation for including polarization in calculations, measurements, and calibrations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

James H. Churnside provided support and helpful discussions during the course of this work.

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